

DIFFICULTIES TO EFFICIENT USAGE OF POINT-OF-SALE MACHINE BY ENTREPRENEURS IN BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract: This study examined the constraints to efficient usage of Point of Sale machines by Entrepreneurs in Rivers State. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 3,201 small and medium scale enterprise owners. Taro Yamane formula was used to arrive at the sample size of 356 respondents. A self-structured questionnaire was subjected to face and content validation by three experts, their corrections and suggestions were effected by the researcher. Cronbach alpha method via SPSS was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. A reliability coefficient value of 0.83 was obtained. The research with the help to two researcher assistance administered 356 copies of the instrument and retrieved 350 copies. Mean and standard deviation were to answer research questions and t-test was used to test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the conclusion, the researcher recommended that: commercial banks should provide adequate infrastructures for effect usage of POS machines by small and medium scale enterprises owners in Rivers State, the operators of POS machines and banks should reduce transaction cost and also ensure that efficient security measures are put in place to protect POS machines users and their customers form fraud risk.

INTRODUCTION

Constraints significantly affects Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) owner's ability to fully maximize the benefits to Point-of-Sale (POS) System (Patrick, & Akintnonye, 2024). The Point of Sales (POS) system has become an essential tool in Nigeria's transition towards a cashless economy. It enables SMEs to conduct fast, secure and convenient financial transactions, thereby improving business efficiency and customer satisfaction. (Ogunsuyi & Siyanbola, 2021). Despite these advantages, the efficient usage of POS machines among SMEs especially in regions like Rivers State remains constrained by several operational, infrastructural and economic challenges.

According to Akerejola and Okpara (2019) stated that, POS adoptions enhances business performance, its usage is hindered by infrastructural deficits, high transaction costs, and security concerns. A point of sale (POS) machine is an electronic device that facilitates cashless transactions between merchants and customers. It plays a vital role in improving transaction accuracy, reducing cash handling risks, and enhancing operational efficiency in SMEs. Small and Medium Scale Enterprise (SMEs), on the other hand are critical drives of economic growth in Nigeria, contributing to employment generation and poverty reduction (Jim & Ernest, 2022). However, their limited resources make them more vulnerable to technological and infrastructural challenges.

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Efficient usage of POS is generally faced with some challenges such as: inadequate infrastructures, high transactions cost, security concerns and fraud, lack of technical knowledge, maintenance and operational issues (Iwemi, 2020). Poor internet connectivity and unstable electricity supply are major barriers to point of sale (POS) usage. Point of Sale machines rely on network availability and power to function effectively frequent outages disrupt transaction and discourage usage.

Banks and financial institutions charge fees on POS transactions these costs reduce profit margins for SMEs and sometimes lead to increased prices for customers, discouraging adoption. Cyber fraud, card cloning, and unauthorized transactions create fear among both business owners and customers. This reduces trust in Point of Sale (POS) system and limits their usage. Many small and medium scale enterprise operators lack adequate training on how to use Point of Sale (POS) systems effectively, leading to operational inefficiencies and reluctance to adopt the technology. Frequent system failures, network errors, and maintenance costs affect the reliability of Point of Sale machines, especially in less developed areas.

Small and medium scale enterprises are business with limited employees, assets and revenue, as defined by local regulations (Jim, Onoja & Ajinwo, 2024). In Nigeria, small medium scale enterprises typically employ fewer than 250 workers and have assets below N500 million (Akani, 2024). In Rivers State, small and medium enterprises operators in sectors like retail, services agriculture, and manufacturing contributing to local employment and economic activity. Business

Growth of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) refers to the measurable increase in the size, capacity, output, revenue, market share, or overall performance of these enterprises over time. It reflects the process through which small medium enterprises SMEs expand their operations, improve probability, and enhance their competitive position in the market. Business growth refers to the increase in revenue customer base, or operational capacity of small and medium scale enterprises overtime. It includes higher sales, expanded markets or improved profitability (Lebura & Godwin, 2022).

Business growth offers benefits like higher profits, larger market presence, and improved resilience for small medium enterprises attract more customers and investment (Amah & Onyenma, 2020). Business growth of small medium enterprises in Rivers State faces challenges including poor infrastructure. High operation costs and limited access to credit. Economic fluctuations, like exchange rates issues also affect profitability. Studies notes that addressing these barriers is essential for sustained growth (Akani, 2024). To boost business growth, small and medium enterprises in Rivers State can adopt strategies like leveraging social media for marketing and accessing government loans. Training in business management can improve operations. The need for supportive policies and infrastructure to enhance small and medium enterprises SMEs growth (Lebura & Godwin, 2022). Such measures are crucial to creating an enabling environment that SMEs are owned and operated by both male and female groups. Fosters the sustainability and competitiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs

Statement of Problem

The use of point of sale (POS) by small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) plays an important role in the economy of Rivers State and the world at large by creating job and supporting local development. However, many of these business find it hard to grow and remain competitive overtime. Despite these advantage of utilizing Point of Sale machine by Small and Medium Scale Enterprise (SMEs). Certain challenges hinders its efficient operation such as poor internet connection, bank and financial institution charge fees, cyber fraud and other technical issues. Hence, the need to determine the constraints to efficient usage of Point of Sale (POS) machine by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Owners.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine, the constraints to efficient usage Point of Sale machine by small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) owners in Rivers State specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine infrastructural challenges that affects the usage of Point of Sales machine (POS) by Small and Medium Enterprises Owners in Rivers State.
2. Determine the impact of transaction cost on the usage of Point of Sale machine (POS) by small and medium scale enterprises owners in River State.
3. Determine the security challenges in the use of Point of Sale machine by small and medium scale enterprises owners in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the infrastructural challenges that affect the usage of Point of Sale machine by Entrepreneurs in Rivers State?
2. What area the impacts of transaction cost in the usage of Point of Sale machine by Entrepreneurs River State?
3. What are the security challenges encountered by small and medium scale business owners in using Point of Sale machine in Rivers State?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Entrepreneurs in the infrastructural challenges in using Point of Sale machine.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female small and medium scales enterprises owners on the transaction cost impact in the usage of Point of Sale machine.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female small and medium scale enterprises owners on the security challenges encountered in the usage of Point of Sale machine.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in Rivers State particularly Port Harcourt metropolis. The population of the study consisted of 3201 small and medium scale enterprises owners in River State. Taro-yamane formula was used to determine a sample size of 356 respondents for the study. A self-structured questionnaire was used for data collection, on 4 point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (DA) and Strongly Disagree (SDA). The instrument was subjected to face and content

validations by three experts, two from Business Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation, their corrections and suggestions were effected by the researcher. Cronbach alpha Via SPSS was used to determine the consistency of the instrument and the reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained; which is deemed highly reliable for this study. The researcher with the help two research assistant administered 356 copies of questionnaire to the respondents and 350 were

retrieved mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to test the null-hypothesis at 0.005 level of significance with a giving degree of freedom.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the infrastructural challenges that affect the usage of Point of Sale machine by Entrepreneurs in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Infrastructural Challenges of the Usage of POS machine by Entrepreneurs in Rivers State. N = 356

S/ N	Items	X	SD	Rm k	X	SD	Rm k	X	SD	Rm k
1.	Infrastructural challenges affects POS usage	3.40	0.93	Agree	2.83	0.81	Agree	3.12	0.87	Agree
2.	Power outage affect my POS transactions	2.80	0.91	Agree	2.91	0.83	Agree	2.86	0.87	Agree
3.	Poor internet connectivity impact on your POS usage	3.50	0.88	Agree	3.02	0.79	Agree	3.26	0.84	Agree
4.	I faced challenges accessing maintenance services for POS machines	3.56	0.85	Agree	3.13	0.74	Agree	3.35	0.80	Agree
5.	Inadequacy of infrastructure impacted significantly on my POS business	2.71	0.80	Agree	3.81	0.86	Agree	3.26	0.83	Agree
	Grand Mean / SD	3.19	0.87		3.14	0.80		3.17		

Source: field survey, 2026

The results of Table 1, revealed that all the respondents agreed with items number 1,2,3,4 and 5. This indicated that the Entrepreneurs

agreed with the infrastructural challenges of utilizing Point-of-Sale machines, with the aggregate grand mean value of 3.17.

Research Question 2

What are the impacts of transaction cost in the usage of Point of Sale machine by Entrepreneurs River State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Transaction Cost Challenges of the usage of POS Machine by Entrepreneurs in Rivers State. N = 356

S/N	Items	X	SD	Rmk	X	SD	Rmk	X	SD	Rmk
1.	Cost of POS transaction affect my business profitability	2.88	0.72	Agree	2.67	0.83	Agree	2.76	0.78	Agree
2.	High transaction fees discourage customers from using POS machines	2.56	0.83	Agree	2.72	0.81	Agree	2.64	0.82	Agree
3.	I considered transaction cost when setting prices	2.54	0.76	Agree	2.80	0.76	Agree	2.82	0.76	Agree
4.	I incurred average transaction cost for POS usage in my business	2.81	0.81	Agree	2.83	0.72	Agree	2.82	0.76	Agree
5.	Business owners are satisfied with the current POS transaction costs	2.00	0.88	Disagree	2.13	0.96	Disagree	2.07	0.92	Disagree
	Grand Mean / SD	2.62	0.80		2.63	0.80		2.63		

Source: Field survey, 2026

Results from Table 2, shows that majority of the respondents agreed to items number 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively. Respondents disagreed to item number 5. The aggregate grand mean value of 2.63 indicated that majority of the Entrepreneurs agreed with the transaction cost

impact in using POS machines in their businesses.

Research Question 3

What are the security challenges encountered by small and medium scale business owners in using Point of Sale machine in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Security Challenges of the usage of POS Machine by Entrepreneurs in Rivers State. N = 356

S/N	Items	X	SD	Rmk	X	SD	Rmk	X	SD	Rmk
1.	I experience POS-related security incidences such as fraud	3.20	0.69	Agree	2.90	0.81	Agree	3.05	0.75	Agree
2.	I have concern about POS transaction security	3.12	0.72	Agree	2.86	0.84	Agree	2.99	0.78	Agree
3.	POS machine vulnerable to cyber attacks	3.04	0.78	Agree	2.90	0.81	Agree	2.97	0.80	Agree
4.	I regularly update my POS security measures	3.11	0.75	Agree	3.00	0.78	Agree	3.06	0.77	Agree
5.	Current security measures are sufficient to protect POS transactions	2.80	0.81	Agree	3.14	0.72	Agree	2.97	0.77	Agree
	Grand Mean / SD	3.06	0.80		2.96	0.80		3.01	0.77	

Source: Field survey, 2026

The result of table 3, revealed that all the respondents agreed with items number 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5. This shows that the respondents on the security challenges impacts of using POS machine, with aggregate grand mean value of 3.01.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of the Difference between Male and Female Entrepreneurs on Infrastructural challenges

Group	N	X	SD	df	S/E	t-cal	t-critical	Remark
Male	157	3.14	0.087	354	0.085	0.63	1.96	Retained
Female	199	3.19	0.80					

Table 4 denote the summary of t-test analysis of items 1-5. Results from the shows that t-calculated value of 0.63 was less than the critical table value of 1.96 at 0.005 level of significance and 354 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This shows that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female

Entrepreneurs on the infrastructural challenges in the usage of POS machines.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female small and medium scales enterprises owners on the transaction cost impact in the usage of Point of Sale machine.

Table 5: t-test Analysis of the difference between male and female Entrepreneurs on Transaction cost impact of using POS machine

Group	N	X	SD	df	S/E	t-cal	t-critical	Remark
Male	157	2.62	0.80	354	0.051	0.46	1.96	Retained
Female	199	2.63	0.82					

Results from table 5, revealed that the t-calculated value of 0.46 less than t-table value of 1.96. Hence, the null hypothesis was upheld. Therefore, significant difference does not exists in the mean ratings of male and female Entrepreneurs on the transaction cost in the usage of POS machines.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female small and medium scale enterprises owners on the security challenges encountered in the usage of Point of Sale machine.

Table 6: t-test Analysis of the difference between male and female Entrepreneurs on Security challenges of using POS machine

Group	N	X	SD	df	S/E	t-cal	t-critical	Remark
Male	157	3.06		354	0.031	0.58	1.96	Retained
Female	199	2.96						

Table 6 shows, that the calculated t-value of 0.58 less than t-critical value of 1.96, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant differences in the mean rating of male and female Entrepreneurs on the security challenges encountered in POS machine.

Discussion of Findings

The result of findings in table 1, revealed that majority of the respondent agreed with the infrastructural challenges in the usage of POS machines by Entrepreneurs in Rivers State. This finding is in agreement with finding of Patrick and Akintonye (2024), which stated that small scale business owners that operate

with point of sale machine were faced with technical challenges. The researcher viewed that POS machine users encountered difficulties in their daily transactions.

From the findings of research question 2, it was found that majority of the respondent agreed with transaction cost involved in the usage POS machine by Entrepreneurs in Rivers State. This finding is in consonant with the findings of Ogunsuyi and Siyanbola (2021), opined that POS machine operators faced high cost or charges challenges. The researcher viewed that if cost of transacting with POS machine are minimized and controlled, Entrepreneurs will make more profits and customers encouraged. The researcher opined that if cost of transacting with POS machines are minimize and control, Entrepreneurs will make more profit and customers will be encouraged.

The findings from research question 3, show that all the respondent agreed with the security challenges encountered by Entrepreneurs in the usage of POS machine, such as fraud and cyber related issued. The finding is supported by the finding of Akerejola and Okpara (2019), stated that POS machine users and their customers encountered some security challenges. The research viewed that efficient security measure be maintained and operated by Entrepreneurs to ensure the safety of the business and the customers.

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Finding relating to hypotheses 1 to 3 revealed that t-calculated values of 0.63, 0.46 and 0.58 were retained. This indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female Entrepreneurs on the infrastructural challenged in the usage of Point-of-Sale machines.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that Entrepreneurs in Rivers State faced infrastructural, transaction cost and secondly challenges in usage of Point-of-Sale (POS) machines. These constrains if control measures are taken could help POS machine users improve their profitability and customers encouraged to patronize them.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the researchers recommended that:

1. The commercial banks should provide adequate infrastructures for efficient usage of Point-of-Sale machines by small and medium scale enterprise owners
2. The operators of POS machine (small and medium scale enterprise owners) and the banks should ensure that transaction cost be minimize to a bearable rate
3. The banks and business owners should ensure efficient security measures are put in place to place to protect POS machines users and their potential customers from fraud risk.

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